

Design and Optimization of a New Compact and Totally Decoupled Nanopositioning Stage

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Abstract—MicroLED mass repair is the key to improve transfer yield and reduce costs, the accuracy of traditional macro motor is difficult to meet the requirements of precision alignment. In response to the problem of lacking a high-precision, compact and large-stroke positioning stage for MicroLED mass repair, this paper proposes a nanopositioning stage to compensate the accuracy of macro motors. The nanopositioning stage adopts flexible guiding mechanisms in an asymmetric structure to achieve high decoupling ratio and compact size. The static modeling of the nanopositioning stage is carried out based on the Euler beam theory and compliance modeling theory. Finite element analysis simulation and optimization with ANSYS Workbench has been performed to improve the stroke and reduce the coupling ratio. Finally, the nanopositioning stage gains large stroke in the X-axis and Y-axis directions, i.e., 278 μm , and low coupling rate, i.e., 0.3%.

Keywords—MicroLED defect detection, high decoupling ratio, bridge amplification, nano alignment

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro Light Emitting Diode (MicroLED) represents a new generation of inorganic self-luminous display technology that integrates driving circuits and pixels on a single chip. The pixel size is typically less than 100 μm , the chip pitch is reduced to 5 μm , nearly 8.3 million pixels on a 4K screen, and each pixel can be independently addressed and individually illuminated [1-3]. Due to the small size of MicroLEDs, it is challenging for traditional LED processes to achieve the desired efficiency and precision. Currently, the main bottleneck of MicroLEDs is the mass repair. Adjustment and replacement of the MicroLED chips after the MicroLED mass transfer is a key technology to enhance mass transfer yield [4].

The traditional mechanical system mainly utilizes linear motors and the method has nonlinear factors such as friction and viscosity, which makes it difficult to meet the requirements of high-precision positioning. While, The compliance mechanism is a kind of mechanism with flexure hinges or flexure components, after the advantages of no gap,

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no friction, no lubrication, integrated manufacturing, and no assembly. Thus compliance mechanisms have been widely used in micro-motion stages that need high positioning accuracy.

Conventional the nanopositioning stage has the advantages of high precision and corresponding speed, but simultaneously, it is difficult to avoid the disadvantage of small stroke. Therefore, this paper proposes to stack the nanopositioning stage and macro positioning stage together, as shown in Fig. 1. The macro positioning stage provides large stroke, and the nanopositioning stage provides high-precision positioning. This configuration enables the achievement of large stroke, high precision, and simultaneously fast response, providing an effective solution for mass repair of MicroLED.

Fig. 1. Program of mass repair system for MicroLED.

As an important actuator in micro-positioning systems, nanopositioning stages have attracted considerable interest from both academic and industrial researchers, with plenty of designs and research outcomes emerging from both domestic and international sources. Abraham et al. from Monash University [5], designed a parallel two-degree-of-freedom nanopositioning stage with a wide range of operational capabilities. The mechanism exhibits a stroke range of up to 2.5 mm inches in the X and Y axes, with a resolution of 0.4 μm and a commendable motion decoupling performance. Tian et al. from Tianjin University [6] designed a novel spatially deployable three-degree-of-freedom flexure nanopositioning stage. The authors were inspired by the spreadable structure and designed three basic MAM modules, which were connect with two sets of hooks. This resulted in a reduction of the horizontal plane dimension by 60.94%, and the maximum displacements of this nanopositioning

stage were 177.33 μm , 179.30 μm , and 17.45 μm in the X, Y, and Z axes, respectively. Zhang et al. from Shanghai University [7] proposed a mathematical model that can accurately calculate the amplification ratio of the bridge-type amplification mechanism, considering the influence of the driving force on the amplification mechanism, and established a nanopositioning stage, with amplification ratios of 5.83 and 5.71 for the direction-ward and direction-ward motions, the strokes of 174.9 μm and 171.3 μm , and the cross-coupling error of less than 3%.

As can be seen from the research results and development trends at home and abroad, many scholars have conducted extensive research on the nanopositioning stage, but there are fewer studies on the nanopositioning stage for MicroLED package alignment. The stage needs large stroke, high precision, no coupling, and other performance requirements, so it is necessary to put forward new design ideas to meet its needs, and the development of novel configuration and excellent performance of the micro-nano positioning stage is of great significance.

In this paper, a nanopositioning stage with large stroke and high decoupling ratio is proposed for MicroLED chips alignment. The stage mainly contains a parallel self-decoupling design and a bridge amplification mechanism, driven by the piezoelectric ceramic actuator to output to the working stage. A static model of the nanopositioning stage is established based on the compliance theory and Eulerian Bernoulli beam theory. Besides, the displacement output of the mechanism is improved and the coupling ratio is reduced through finite element simulation and multi-objective optimization.

II. MECHANICAL DESIGN

The nanopositioning stage is not only an important component of the nanopositioning system, but also the focus of this paper. The piezoelectric ceramic is the driving element of the nanopositioning stage, and the bridge amplifier is the displacement amplifier of the nanopositioning stage. An asymmetric guiding mechanism is adopted to achieve a self-decoupling design. The bridge-type amplification mechanism is connected to the output platform by a flexure beam, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Structure of nanopositioning stage.

The piezoelectric ceramic driver outputs force and displacement, amplified by a bridge amplification mechanism and output to a flexure beam. Finally acts on the output platform to realize the motion in the direction of the X or Y-axis. According to the MicroLED massive transfer

repair requirements, the stroke of the nanopositioning stage in the X and Y-axis must not be less than 250 μm , and the coupling rate must not be more than 1%.

The static performance of the nano-positioner stage, such as the stiffness of the mechanism, the motion stroke, and the coupling rate, are the key factors in measuring the performance of the nanopositioning stage [8]. The bridge amplification mechanism and flexure guiding mechanism are analyzed by hydrostatic modeling, and then finite element simulation is used to verify the accuracy of the models.

A. Modeling of straight beam flexure hinge

As shown in Fig. 3, for a straight beam flexure hinge moving in the plane, there are three types of forces at the free end [9]: tensile force or pressure F_x in the x-direction, shear force F_y in the y-direction, and force coupling M_z around the z-axis. There are also three types of displacements at the free end: a linear displacement Δx in the x-direction, a linear displacement Δy in the y-direction, and an angular displacement $\Delta\theta_z$ in the z-direction, where F_x produces a linear displacement Δx in the x-direction, and both F_y and M_z produce a linear displacement Δy in the y-direction and an angular displacement $\Delta\theta_z$ in the y-direction.

Fig. 3. The straight beam flexure hinge.

According to the elastic beam theory and the assumption of minimum deformation, the static characteristics of the flexible mechanism can be expressed in terms of the flexure matrix [10]. The straight beam type flexure hinge displacement load relationship can be written in the following form:

$$T_E = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x \\ \Delta y \\ \Delta\theta_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{x,F_x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_{y,F_y} & C_{y,M_z} \\ 0 & C_{\theta_z,F_y} & C_{\theta_z,M_z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F_x \\ F_y \\ M_z \end{bmatrix} = C_E W_E \quad (1)$$

where C_{x,F_x} , C_{y,F_y} , C_{y,M_z} , C_{θ_z,F_y} and C_{θ_z,M_z} are the flexibility coefficient matrices of the straight beam type flexible hinge.

In flexure modelling, the model needs to be built in the same coordinate system, which requires a rotational transformation R and a translational transformation t of the coordinate system of each cell. as shown in Eq. 2.

$$R_z = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_z & -\sin \theta_z & 0 \\ \sin \theta_z & \cos \theta_z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{t} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -z & y \\ z & 0 & -x \\ -y & x & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where R_z is the rotation matrix of the coordinate transformation and t is the translation vector, the accompanying matrix of the coordinate transformation and its transpose matrix are:

$$Ad = \begin{bmatrix} R & 0 \\ TR & R \end{bmatrix}, \quad Ad^T = \begin{bmatrix} R^T & -R^T \hat{t} \\ 0 & R^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The transformations of the flexure matrix in different coordinate systems are related by:

$$C' = Ad \times C \times Ad^T \quad (4)$$

After unifying the coordinate system, operations are performed according to the series-parallel relationship to obtain the flexure input matrix or flexure output matrix of the overall structure. Assuming that the flexure cell flexure matrix is C_{si} , the series flexure matrix is:

$$C_s = \sum_{i=1}^n Ad_i C_{si} Ad_i^T \quad (5)$$

Assuming that the flexure matrix of the flexure unit is C_{pj} , the parallel flexure matrix is:

$$C_p = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n (Ad_j C_{pj} Ad_j^T)^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (6)$$

B. Modeling of flexible guiding mechanism

The flexible guiding mechanism of the nanopositioning stage is composed of three kinds of flexure beams, beam ① is an equal-armed short L-type beam, beam ② is an equal-armed long L-type beam, and beam ③ is an equal-armed long T-type beam, all of which are composed of equal-thickness and equal-width flexible straight beams as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Flexible guiding mechanism.

Taking the flexible beam ①②③ as an example, the displacement-load relationship from the flexible beam ①②③ to the output is obtained by the compliance theory and coordinate change:

$$\begin{cases} x_{12} = l_1, R = R_z \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \right), \\ y_{12} = 0 \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} x_{12o} = l_{11}, R = 1 \\ y_{12o} = l_{12} \end{cases} \\ \begin{cases} x_{21} = l_2, R = R_z \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \right), \\ y_{21} = 0 \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} x_{22o} = l_{22}, R = 1 \\ y_{22o} = l_{33} \end{cases} \\ \begin{cases} x_{32} = l_3, R = 1, \\ y_{32} = 0 \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} x_{32o} = l_{33}, R = 1 \\ y_{32o} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Combining Eqs. (3)-(7), the flexure output matrix C_{o1}' of the upper right branch can be obtained as:

$$C_{o1}' = \left(\left(\sum_{i=1}^2 Ad_i C_i Ad_i^T \right)^{-1} + \left(\sum_{j=2}^2 Ad_j C_j Ad_j^T \right)^{-1} + \left(\sum_{z=3}^2 Ad_z C_z Ad_z^T \right)^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the output matrices $C1, C2, C3$ of the other three flexure chains can be obtained, and the output matrix of the guiding mechanism can be obtained according to the parallel relationship:

$$C_o = \left((C_{o1}')^{-1} + (C_{o2}')^{-1} + (C_{o3}')^{-1} + (C_{o4}')^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (9)$$

C. Modeling of bridge amplification mechanism

Bridge amplification mechanisms are often designed as symmetrical structures. As shown in Fig. 5, the elongation under the piezoelectric ceramic actuator is Δx on both sides and the total displacement of the output is $2\Delta y$ [11], so the ideal amplification λ of the mechanism is:

$$\lambda = \frac{2\Delta y}{2\Delta x} = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 5. Analysis of bridge amplification mechanism.

As shown in Fig. 6, where F is the input force, L_b, B and C are the length, thickness and width of the simply supported beam, E is the Young's modulus of the material, and the output force of the piezoelectric ceramic is applied at the middle of the input.

Fig. 6. The designed bridge amplification mechanism.

Due to the symmetrical structure of the bridge mechanism, the following results can be derived from the force balance relationship:

$$F_1 = F_2 = F_x \quad (11)$$

$$M_1 = M_2 = M = \frac{F_x l_c}{2} \quad (12)$$

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{l_c}{l_a} \quad (13)$$

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{l_0}{l_a} \quad (14)$$

where α is the deflection angle between the two hinges, l_a , l_c , l_0 are the linear, vertical and horizontal distances between the hinges respectively.

In this paper, we only consider the plane deformation of the flexure hinge. Based on the compliance theory in the literature [12], the straight beam flexure hinge output can be simplified as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta x_i \\ \Delta y_i \\ \Delta \theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{l}{Ebt} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{4l^3}{3Ebt^3} + \frac{l}{Gbt} & \frac{6l^2}{Ebt^3} \\ 0 & \frac{6l^2}{Ebt^3} & \frac{12l}{Ebt^3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F_x \\ 0 \\ M \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where E is the Young's modulus of the material, G is the shear modulus, and l , t and b denote the length, width and thickness of the hinge respectively.

In order to further investigate the deformation of the bridge mechanism, the tensile deformation of the bridge arm during the amplification process is considered:

$$\Delta l = \frac{l_a \cos \alpha}{EA} F_x \quad (16)$$

where $A = bc$ is the cross-sectional area of the bridge arms (HI , JK , LO , GN).

Due to the deformation of the flexure hinge, the bridge arm (HI , JK , LO , GN) rotates and extends, resulting in:

$$\Delta x = 2\Delta x_i + l_a \sin \alpha \Delta \theta + \Delta l \cos \alpha \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta y = 2\Delta y_i + l_a \cos \alpha \Delta \theta + \Delta l \sin \alpha \quad (18)$$

The input displacement and output displacement can be obtained by associating Eqs. (13)-(18), respectively:

$$\Delta x = \left(\frac{2l}{Ebt} + \frac{l_0^2}{EAl_a} + \frac{6l_l^2}{Ebt^3} \right) F_x \quad (19)$$

$$\Delta y = \left(\frac{6l^2 l_c + 6ll_0 l_c + l_0 l_c}{Ebt^3} + \frac{l_0 l_c}{EAl_a} \right) F_x \quad (20)$$

Therefore, the amplification λ of the bridge mechanism is:

$$\lambda = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} = \frac{\frac{6l^2 l_c + 6ll_0 l_c + l_0 l_c}{bt^3} + \frac{l_0 l_c}{Al_a}}{\frac{2l}{bt} + \frac{l_0^2}{Al_a} + \frac{6ll_c^2}{bt^3}} \quad (21)$$

Since $A = bc$, Eq. (21) can be simplified to:

$$\lambda = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} = \frac{\frac{6l^2 l_c + 6ll_0 l_c + l_0 l_c}{t^3} + \frac{cl_a}{cl_a}}{\frac{2l}{t} + \frac{l_0^2}{cl_a} + \frac{6ll_c^2}{t^3}} \quad (22)$$

III. FINITE ELEMENTS ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION

In order to verify the results of the model, the finite element analysis software ANSYS Workbench is used for simulation and analysis to verify the accuracy of the hydrostatic modeling of the micro-nano positioning stage. The displacement of the piezoelectric ceramic actuator is simulated by inputting the determined displacement, and the output displacement amplified by the bridge mechanism is obtained. The material is selected as Al-7075, whose Young's modulus E is 72 GPa, Poisson's ratio μ is 0.33, the yield limit δ_s of the material is 505 MPa, and the density is 2810 kg/m³; the piezoelectric ceramic actuator is model of PSt150/7/40 VS12 ball-head type, whose nominal stroke is 38 μ m, and the main dimensional parameters of the nanopositioning stage are shown in Table I, which is used to perform the stage simulation analysis.

TABLE I. INITIAL DESIGN PARAMETERS

Parameter	Numeric value	Parameter	Numeric value
t /mm	0.8	l /mm	5.0
b /mm	5.0	l_0 /mm	13
l_c /mm	1.0	l_1 /mm	13
l_b /mm	16	l_2 /mm	17

When the input displacement of the bridge amplification mechanism is assigned as 38 μ m, as shown in Fig. 7, the maximum output displacements of the nanopositioning stage in the X-axis direction and Y-axis direction are 230.21 μ m and 230.6 μ m, respectively, and the coupling rates in the X-axis direction and Y-axis direction are 2.18% and 2.21%, respectively, which do not satisfy the design requirements and need to be optimized further.

Fig. 7. Static analysis of the designed stage. (a) Deformation in the X-axis direction; (b) Deformation in the Y-axis direction.

From the above equations, it can be seen that the stroke and displacement coupling of the nanopositioning stage is mainly related to the lengths l_1 and l_2 of the equal-armed L-type beam, as well as the lengths l and widths t of the hinges of the bridge-type mechanism, and the dimensions of the vertical distance l_c and horizontal distance l_0 between the hinges, which can be optimized by adjusting the dimensional parameters of the mechanism.

Multi-objective optimization of the stage carried out by using ANSYS Workbench and the optimization algorithm chosen is Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm, which can solve for different optimization parameters concerning the output results and recommends the optimal solution. The objective of the optimization is to obtain a larger output displacement and smaller displacement coupling ratio for the

output platform in the micro-nano positioning stage, and the range of each parameter is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS OF THE OPTIMIZATION

Parameter	Value range	Parameter	Value range
t /mm	0.4-1	l /mm	4-6
l_1 /mm	12-15	l_0 /mm	10-14
l_2 /mm	16-19	l_c /mm	0.5-2

To achieve higher accuracy in optimization, it is necessary to calculate sufficient design points. A total of 1200 design points were collected in this optimization. Due to the presence of decimals in the optimized dimensions, the dimensional parameters of the optimized mechanism are approximated for ease of machining, and the final dimensional parameters are shown in Table III.

TABLE III. OPTIMIZED DESIGN PARAMETERS

Parameter	Numeric value	Parameter	Numeric value
t /mm	0.9	l /mm	4.5
l_1 /mm	14.7	l_0 /mm	13.7
l_2 /mm	18.4	l_c /mm	1

When the input displacement of the bridge amplification mechanism is assigned as $38 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in Fig. 8(a-b), the maximum output displacements of the nanopositioning stage in the X-axis direction are $278.07 \mu\text{m}$ and the maximum stress is 131.88 MPa , respectively; as shown in Fig. 8(c-d), the maximum output displacements in the Y-axis direction are $278.07 \mu\text{m}$ and the maximum stress is 133.3 MPa , respectively.

Fig. 8. Deformation and Stress Map. (a) Deformation in the X-axis direction; (b) Stress in the X-axis direction; (c) Deformation in the Y-axis direction; (d) Stress in the Y-axis direction.

After optimization, the maximum output of the nanopositioning stage in the X-axis direction and Y-axis direction is improved by 20.79% and 20.59%, respectively,

and the coupling ratio in the X-axis direction and Y-axis direction is 0.26% and 0.25%, respectively.

The nanopositioning stage is commonly used in high-frequency response operations, so its resonance frequency must be analyzed. The resonant mode shapes and frequencies of the nanopositioning stage structure are simulated through modal analysis to check the dynamic performance of the nanopositioning stage structure. The first frequency of the nanopositioning stage is 380.79 Hz , and the second frequency is 382.11 Hz , and its modal shape is the output platform moving in the XY plane, as shown in Fig. 9(a-b). The third frequency of the nanopositioning stage is 522.83 Hz , and the fourth frequency is 764 Hz , and its modal shape is that the output platform and the bridge amplification mechanism in the nanopositioning stage rotates in the XY plane, as shown in Fig. 9(c-d). The nanopositioning stage has a better dynamic performance, which can satisfy the operation of high-frequency response.

Fig. 9. Modal analysis of a nanopositioning stage. (a) The first direction; (b) The second order; (c) The third order; (d) The fourth order.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a totally decoupled and compact micro-nanopositioning stage with relatively large stroke is proposed. The mathematic modeling is performed and FEA simulation is carried out to verify the results of the modeling. Then, the multi-objective optimization is presented and the stroke and decoupling ratio have been improved. The strokes of the nanopositioning stage are $278.07 \mu\text{m}$ and $278.07 \mu\text{m}$ in X axis and Y axis, improved by more than 20% after optimization. Meanwhile, the coupling ratios are reduced from 2.18% and 2.21% to 0.26% and 0.25%, showing totally decoupled property. The first-order frequency of the nanopositioning stage is 380.79 Hz , which can meet the design requirements of high frequency. To conclude, the proposed nanopositioning stage has high decoupling ratio and compact size, which is promising to compensate the low accuracy in macro motor for MicroLED mass repair.

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